

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATING A DICTIONARY OF SYNONYMS IN FORMING SPEECH VOLUME

Sharofat Toshmirzayeva

Independent researcher,

Alisher Navo'i Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and
Literature. sharofat.m.t@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article theoretically analyzes the phenomenon of synonymy, presents the characteristics of lexical synonyms, which are considered the most active manifestation of the phenomenon of synonymy, and puts forward ideas on how to interpret and present these units in dictionaries. Also, the importance of using synonym dictionaries in the lesson is revealed, and the educational importance of students forming synonym dictionaries is explained. Sample tasks in this regard are shown, and the expected results are explained.

Synonyms are linguistic units that demonstrate the richness of speech, clearly express the content of thoughts, and prevent unnecessary repetitions. Synonyms (referred to as "ma'nodoshlar" in some textbooks and manuals) have been given various definitions. "Synonyms (from Greek "synonymos" meaning "same name") are words with the same unifying meaning but different additional shades of meaning and spellings". (Askarova et al., 1972, p. 42)

According to M. Askarova, "Words with different spellings and pronunciations but the same unifying meaning are called synonyms. A synonymous series is a collection of synonyms united around one meaning, and the word expressing a neutral lexical meaning or more characteristic of literary speech within this series is called the dominant" (Askarova et al. 1972, p. 45).

According to R. Sayfullayeva, "Lexemes that are different in form but express the same concept with various connotations and nuances are called synonyms" (Sayfullayeva et al. 2009, p. 112).

Z. Kholmanova defines these linguistic units as follows: "Words that are close in meaning to each other, even if they have different forms, are called synonyms. The expression of one (same) meaning through several word forms creates synonyms. The synonymous relationship between words is called the phenomenon of synonymy" (Kholmanova, 2017, p. 92).

G. Abdurahmonov explains that "a synonym is the expression of one characteristic, object, person, or event by several names" (Abdurahmonov et al., 1995, p. 101).

"Synonyms are words that have the same general meaning, but differ in subtle nuances of meaning, with different pronunciations and spellings" (Rafiyev, 2014, p. 78).

"Words or affixes expressing a common meaning are called synonyms. Words and affixes that are in a synonymous relationship are called a synonym nest or a series of synonyms. A

member of a series of synonyms that is free from any stylistic peculiarity and speaker's evaluation is called a dominant" (Nurmonov et al., 2013, p. 227).

A comprehensive definition of the phenomenon of synonymy in Uzbek linguistics belongs to the renowned linguist Academician A. Hojiyev: "The uniformity of the meaning of synonyms does not negate that they have different characteristics. On the contrary, the existence of several words in the language to express one meaning indicates that synonyms do not fully correspond to each other in all respects, and each of them has its own distinctive features. Since the words that make up the synonymous series differ from each other in certain aspects, they have the ability to exist in the language as separate lexical units" (Shoabdurahmonov, 1980, p. 115).

In linguistics, the following types of synonyms are distinguished:

- lexical synonyms;
- phraseological synonyms;
- grammatical synonyms;
- proverb synonyms;
- descriptive expression synonyms.

It is known that in the conceptual foundations of native language education in secondary schools, two essential tools are emphasized: textbooks and dictionaries. One of the crucial factors in developing students' creative thinking and speech is working with dictionaries. Dictionaries create an invaluable and rich vocabulary that fosters students' creative thinking, independent reasoning, and fluent expression of creative ideas in both oral and written forms. Today, in developed countries, hundreds of specialized dictionaries have been created for each level of education (from kindergarten to university). While there are about 30 educational dictionaries for Russian schools, there is only one "Spelling Dictionary" for Uzbek schools. It is an urgent task to create explanatory dictionaries, synonym dictionaries, antonym dictionaries, gradation dictionaries, dictionaries of obsolete words, dialect dictionaries, idiom dictionaries, collocation dictionaries, thesauri, homonym dictionaries, word structure dictionaries, pronunciation dictionaries, as well as separate terminological dictionaries and encyclopedias for each subject. Without creating necessary dictionaries for students, it is impossible to develop creative thinking, and current textbooks, which are meant to develop oral and written speech, cannot fully fulfill their function. This necessitates the development and compilation of principles for creating thematic educational dictionaries for the secondary education level [Mengliev, 2006: 6].

Today, as language is viewed as a system, the question of semantic relationships between linguistic units, their similarities and differences, is attracting the interest of many linguists. Until the 1940s-1990s, inter-word semantic relations were limited to synonymy and antonymy. Recent observations based on systemic analysis methods have revealed that semantic relationships in our language are diverse, distinguishing types such as graduonymy, hyponymy, paronymy, functionary, and hierarchonymy. Consequently, differentiating between synonyms and graded words has become a current requirement for students. Lexical synonymy is a relationship between lexemes expressing the same object, property, action, or state, where the semes of nomination and function are identical, but the semes of expression differ. Gradation, on the other hand, involves lexemes with the same general nominative semes but representing

different degrees of a particular seme. Furthermore, the second difference between synonymy and gradation is that while lexemes in a synonymous series differ in their expressive semes, this is not a necessary condition in a gradation series. In our linguistics, scholar Sh. Orifjonova, who specifically studied graded words, emphasizes that the lexical paradigm in graduonyms unites around one dominant word. She notes that the meanings of the words “window” and “gate” are defined in relation to the dominant word “door” [Orifjonova, 1996: 19] and includes them in the category of graded words.

We know that among the communicative qualities of speech, its richness is of particular importance. The most crucial factor in creating speech richness is the phenomenon of synonymy. The main goal of native language education in schools, along with developing qualities such as correctness, accuracy, purity, expressiveness, logic, and appropriateness in students' speech, is to enhance the quality of speech richness. We believe that a dictionary of synonyms, compiled for specific grade levels, is one of the primary factors in increasing speech richness. In such dictionaries, it is advisable to have a vocabulary of 100-200 words, appropriate to the student's age. The teacher can distribute the dictionary to students at the beginning of each quarter and check it at the end of the quarter, or assign it to students as an independent task.

An example of creating such a dictionary is recommended. Dictionary of synonyms for 5th grade (example). About 100 words, recommended for the 1st quarter, the rest in Appendix 2)

1st quarter

Headword of a synonymous series	Synonyms	Obsolete, borrowing, dialect words
Vatan (motherland)	yurt, o'lka, mamlakat, diyor, makon, mulk,	polis
Shoh (king)	podshoh, sulton, qirol	xoqon
Xalq(public)	el, elat, millat	ulus, bo'dun
mo'tabar(dear)		
baxmal		
shonli		
Pinhona(secret)		
Ayovsiz(merciless)		
Tarsaki (slap)		
Quvnoq (funny)		
Jonajon (dear)		
Payt (moment)		
Ovqat (meal)		

Navo(sound)		
mo'jaz(gina) (miraculously)		
Kitob (book)		
Mushtlashmoq(fihgt)		
Sehr (magic)		
Uzr(sorry, apologize)		
Toza (fresh)		
yengil (ish) (light work)		
Qattiq (hard)		
Hayratlanmoq(to be surprised)		
Kulmoq (luagh)		

Grade 5. Independent work

Headword of a synonymous series	Synonyms	Obsolete, borrowing, dialect words
xo'tik (colt)	eshak bolasi, xo'tikcha	qudung, kudung, kurra (shevada)
Natija(result)	oqibat, pirovard	
karam (insoniy fazilat) (generosity (human virtue))		
Birpas (one moment)		
Istak (wish)		
Burch(duty)		
Xotirjamlik (calmness)		

Grade 9 (around 140 words, recommended for 1st quarter, rest in Appendix 2.1)

1st quarter

Words	Synonyms	Obsolete, borrowing, dialect words
Uy-joy(Housing)	boshpana, xonadon, uy-ro'zg'or, boshpana, makon	ma'vo
yolg'on (lie)	aldamchilik, xiyonat	o'tirik, feyk
Tadbirkorlik (entrepreneurship)	tijorat, ishbilarmonlik, omilkorlik, uddaburonlik	biznes

Odam (human)	inson, bashar, kimsa, odamzod, banda, baniodam, banibashar	ins, xilqat
Sohibqiron (king)	jahongir, olamgir	jahondor
Shumtaka (joke)	Tirrancha, zumrasha, jinqarcha, tirmizak,	erdoncha
Ichkilik (alcohol)		boda
Tasavvur (Imagination)		taxayyul
Xalq (public)		ahl, mardum
Xató (error)		sahv, sakta
Yashirincha (secret)		nihon
Yosh (young)		navras
Yuz (face)		angor, oraz, ruxsor,
Shartnoma (agreement)		kontrakt, bay
Chamasi (approximately)		g'olibo
Chunki (because)		zotan
Mansabdorlar (officials)		arkon
Ahvol (situation)		kepata(sheva)
Ahil (sharing)		bahamjihat
Dushman (enemy)		aduv, yog'iy
Hayoli(polite)		afifa
cho'loq (lame)		lang
cho'l(desert)		bodiya(eskirgan)
Chumoli (ant)		mo 'rcha
Chaqmoq (lightning)		yeldirim
Chanqoq(Thirsty)		yutoq
Behuda (in vain)		abas
Shubhali (suspicious)		bejo
Shifokor(doctor)		emchi
Shayton (devil)		la'in

Students receive this assignment at the beginning of the quarter as a quarterly task and must complete it by the end of the quarter. They are given small recommendations in the form of a roadmap for completing the task, and advisory cooperation between the teacher and the student continues throughout. In this process, the student creates synonymous forms of lexemes that they have read or used in their own speech or in the speech of family members. When faced with difficulties, they are guided by their parents and subject teacher.

These tasks serve to develop general competencies in students, such as a sense of responsibility and concentration, as well as linguistic competencies like speech observation, differentiating and separating speech units from one another, and semantic analysis.

The Uzbek language has long been distinguished from other languages by its abundance of synonymous words. Synonymy provides the opportunity to express ideas in various ways.

The appeal of a speaker's (or writer's) speech depends on their mastery of synonyms during school education and regular completion of exercises and assignments related to synonymy. Reading literary works and developing skills in working with texts are also essential tools for ensuring richness of speech.

In conclusion, it can be said that to ensure students acquire synonyms and actively use these linguistic units in their speech, it is first necessary to elevate these units to the status of active elements in their mental lexicon. To achieve this, synonyms should be actively employed both in the educational process and in communication. Additionally, it is beneficial to develop the skill of identifying and analyzing synonyms during literature lessons and when reading literary works. We are confident that teaching students to compile small synonym dictionaries as independent assignments will further accelerate this process.

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